

Pulmonary dendritic cells (CD11b^{hi} CD14^{hi} DC) are enriched for nestin.

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Analysis of nestin expression in the lung revealed a population of hematopoietic-derived cells of the respiratory tract expressing high levels of nestin: these were pulmonary dendritic cells (CD11b^{hi} CD14^{hi} DC).

Citations

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